

Online Payment Fraud Be the Emerger of Perceptional Risk towards the Digital Payment System

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Abstract

Digital payment System is the best example for unity in diversity as it is widely accepted by the citizens. With digitalization of payment new term also came into picture i.e. Online payment fraud. Online Payment Fraud is nothing but the use of vulnerabilities of online payment system like mobile banking, internet banking etc. The increase in number of online payment fraud has depleted the goodwill of digital payment system. Thus, the study aims to determine the factors that could lead to Online Payment Fraud and how it is affecting the mindset of the customers of the digital payment system. The results revealed five factors that could lead to Online Payment Fraud. However, which affects the mindset is the precautions about the account details that made them worried about the risk of using digital payment system.

Keywords: Online Payment Fraud, Digital Payment Systems, Perceived Security Risk, KMO test.

I. INTRODUCTION

India is a country with varied demography and culture making it suitable to accept any new technology sooner (Shrivastava,2024). One such aim is Digital Economy by which government is targeting to access all the citizens electronically (Rani,2021). For achieving this aim Digital Payment System into existence in 2016, the government also introduced demonetization for making it popular. However, the desired popularity was attained after the hitting of COVID -19 pandemic (Badak et al; 2023). However, people were inclined towards the usage of cash payment method only (Sivathanu;2017) because of the risk associated with digital payment transactions. The fear of using of digital payment system was fueled by the increment in the number of online payment fraud (Verma,2020). Tiwari and Sharma (2021) have stated that digital payment system evolution also brought in the illegal practice also. People have become habituated for using the digital payment system that fraud doesn't bothers also. However, PWC Report,2022 have showed that online payment frauds are

increasing at an alarming rate, which is also supported by RBI Annual Report 2021. Pandey 2022 has stated that the increase in the number of online payment fraud would affect the goodwill of the digital payment system. But what actually matters is the customers awareness towards the digital payment system and how to deal with these frauds (Johari & Kumar; 2023). Chandrasekaran & Narayanan (2019) have stated that the digital payment system provides freedom to individual to access their money but due to lack of awareness, ease of use, cost, security, etc. the complete utilization is still not achieved due to which people have doubt in using it but out of habit can't stop using it also. (Shrivastava;2024).

In 2012, Kesharwani & Bisht brought a new construct of Perceived Risk which could impact the intention to use the digital payment system. In support to this Reepu & Arora, 2022 have stated that there are antecedents attached to the perceived risk which could impact the intention of using the digital payment system. Zhao et al (2008) have identified three elements of risk which are performance risk, privacy risk and social risk. Bazgosha et al; 2012 have added five more elements of risk which are security risk, financial risk, time risk, psychological risk, and social risk that can affect the usage of digital payment system.

Research Gap & Research Problem

The data set provided by the financial institution shows that online payment fraud is increasing at startling rate. There could be numerous reasons out of which one is identified by Johari & Kumar; 2023 i.e. lack of awareness among the customers. Pandey 2022 highlighted that online payment fraud is hampering the goodwill of the digital payment system. Thus, the study tries determine the reasons that could lead to online payment fraud as per customer and how it is impacting their mindset to use digital payment system in terms of security and financial risk.

The research problem identified is the reasons of the increment of online payment should be known to everyone so that it could dealt with, the customers feel secure enough to carry out the transaction on digital platform without any doubt of risk in their mind.

Objectives of the Study

- To determine the reasons leading to the Online Payment Fraud.
- To examine the impact of reasons on the Perceived Financial risk and Perceived Security risk.

II. Data & Methodology

The research design chosen for the study was exploratory and causal in nature. The study was conducted in Indore City. The respondents were chosen via convenient sampling and were given self- structured questionnaire for recording their responses. The questionnaire had three sections, section one dealt with demographics attributes, second and third section had

questions based on 5-point Likert Scale. In total 111 respondents have responded out of 150, thus, the sample size chosen for the study was 111. The research tools applied are as follows:

- Cronbach alpha test-
Cronbach alpha test was used to check the reliability of the data set.
- Exploratory Factor Analysis-
Exploratory Factor Analysis (Principal Component Analysis) is a tool which comprises of multiple tools in it. The KMO test is used for checking the sample adequacy of the data set received. The Bartlett's test of Sphericity is used for checking the correlation among the variables. Varimax rotation was used to extract the factors with maximum variations.
- Multiple Variable Regression
In order to know the impact of factors on the sorest spot of the risk associated with digital payment systems are financial risk and security risk.
Equation 1: $Y_{1i} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 F_{1i} + \beta_2 F_{2i} + \beta_3 F_{3i} + \beta_4 F_{4i} + \beta_5 F_{5i} + \beta_6 \text{Age} + \beta_7 \text{Gender} + \epsilon_i$
Equation 2: $Y_{2i} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 F_{1i} + \alpha_2 F_{2i} + \alpha_3 F_{3i} + \alpha_4 F_{4i} + \alpha_5 F_{5i} + \alpha_6 \text{Age} + \alpha_7 \text{Gender} + \epsilon_i$
Here,
 Y_{1i} - Perceived Financial Risk
 Y_{2i} - Perceived Security Risk
 $F_{1i}, F_{2i}, \dots, F_{5i}$ - Factors received from Factor Analysis
 β_0, α_0 – Intercept of respective equations
 $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_7$ -coefficient of variables in Equation 1
 $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_7$ - coefficient of variables in Equation 2
 ϵ_i - error term

III. Findings & Implications

Table 1
Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.843	18

The above table reveals the Cronbach alpha value to be 0.843 which is considered good for carrying out the study.

Table 2
KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.704
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	569.857
	Df	153
	Sig.	.000

The value obtained is 0.704 which is greater than 0.5 means the sample is adequate enough to carry out the factor analysis.

The value obtained 0.000 which is less than 0.05 leading to confirmation that there is correlation among the variables in the data set.

Table 3
Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
OPF01	1.000	.686
OPF02	1.000	.741
OPF03	1.000	.742
OPF04	1.000	.535
OPF05	1.000	.595
OPF06	1.000	.648
OPF07	1.000	.682
OPF08	1.000	.815
OPF09	1.000	.691

OPF10	1.000	.787
OPF11	1.000	.724
OPF12	1.000	.638
OPF13	1.000	.733
OPF14	1.000	.603
OPF15	1.000	.652
OPF16	1.000	.691
OPF17	1.000	.675
OPF18	1.000	.613

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Communalities table shows that the all the eighteen variables explain the variation in the model significantly as all have the value greater than 0.5.

The total variance explained by the model is 68.060% and five factors were found to have the eigen value greater than one.

Nomenclature of Factors

Factor 1: Precautious about the account details

This factor explains 22.346% of the whole model. It got its name due to the variables like clearing the browsing history after the use of online banking, logging out of the account every time after use, never perform any online transaction from public network, prefer to use two step authentications for payment always see the padlock and 'https' before use of online banking.

Factor 2: Acknowledging my responsibility

It explains 14.134% of the whole model. It earned its name due to the variables like never disclosing my password details of account to anyone, always remembering the usage of QR scan and PIN in any transaction.

Factor 3: Active Vigilance in the System

11.882% of the whole model was explained by it. It includes variables like banks and UPI apps are vigilant about online payment fraud, bank employees are supportive in case fraud occurs as they are equipped well fraud handling situation knowledge. Bank and UPI tries to provide immediate help to its customers who have become the victim of fraud.

Factor 4: Awareness about Online Payment Fraud

This factor explains 11.486% of the whole model. It includes variables like customers are aware about the red flags that could lead to fraud, aware about the documents required while availing any financial services online, aware about how the online payment fraud happens.

Factor 5: Blaming the service provider

8.212% of the whole model is explained. It included variables like weak security system of the financial payment service apps and the banks are responsible for siphoning the money to the fraudsters in case of fraud occurrence.

Multiple Variable Regression

From the table below it is clearly evident that none of the independent variables and controlling variables have impact on the perceived financial risk.

TABLE 4		
Dependent Variable: Perceived Financial Risk		
Independent Variable	Coefficient	T-statistics
Intercept	3.367109	3.197326
Factor1	0.254448	1.325921
Factor 2	-0.14748	-0.88749
Factor 3	0.302768	1.626137
Factor 4	-0.34896	-1.802
Factor 5	-0.13351	-1.03465
Age	0.085334	0.514178
Gender	-0.25988	-1.07971

R²	0.159166	
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From the table below it can be inferred that Factor1 i.e. Precautions about the account details have a positive impact and gender has a negative impact on the perceived security risk. Thus, it could be inferred that males are less bothered about the security risk as compared to females.

TABLE 5		
Dependent Variable: Perceived Security Risk		
Independent Variable	Coefficient	T-statistics
Intercept	2.298169	2.119734
Factor1	0.396769	2.008292
Factor 2	-0.12761	-0.74586
Factor 3	-0.0249	-0.12989
Factor 4	-0.27477	-1.37823
Factor 5	0.185358	1.395331
Age	-0.0639	-0.37399
Gender	-0.75978	-3.06611
R²	0.249584	

IV. Conclusion

The study revealed five factors that could lead to the online payment fraud. the study also revealed that perceived security risk is of main concern to the customers as they are more worried about their account details might be leaked or used by some other person. In particular females are more concerned about it. Along with this the awareness of online payment fraud factor is in line with the study of Johari & Kumar;2023 which highlighted the lack awareness of digital payment system leading to frauds. Currently, the study focusses on one side of the coin i.e. customers of digital payment system for better results the other side i.e. employees should also be considered for making an effective as well as efficient policy to deal with this online payment fraud issue.

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